

Psychology and Truth Behind Cults

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The definition of cult is typically associated with a religion or a religious movement, although it is not. In fact, cult; “[...] is a term that doesn’t refer to religion at all, but is applied to a social movement. Followers see themselves as believers, even disciples—not cult members. “The word ‘cult’ originally designates a practice of religious veneration and the religious system based around such veneration—for example, the cult of Our Lady of Guadalupe,” says Robin Clark, a linguistics professor in the School of Arts and Sciences. “However, the word was co-opted in the first half of the 20th century by sociology, and has come to denote a social group with ‘socially deviant’ beliefs and practices, like a UFO cult” (Rodia, 2019). This paper will explore psychological approaches to understand the human drive to join cults, as well as the psychological effects of joining cults, and the most effective treatment for people who joined cults.

Cults provide their people with their needs in the way that other social structures cannot. For example a person does not need to work in exchange for money. Cults offer an alternative social structure that is more comfortable. While they may require a person to non-question and fully obey their leaders, cults will also provide for basic needs such as shelter, food, and love and belonging. A study of cults, which was done by Columbus State University, suggests that; “[...] there is an evolutionary need for them, for they are used as a means for social bonds and resources”(Carlton Best, 2018). Therefore, Cognitive psychology provides a deeper view on cults themselves. In fact, by studying the way individuals think we gain a deeper insight on how the cults are established. When people face a resonance between their beliefs and the harmful ideology of cults, they may distort their perspectives in order to maintain as a loyal member and in order to remain like everyone else, because in cults their members cannot stand out, everyone must be on a par. This conflict between cult members beliefs and the cults ideology, causes a cognitive dissonance (Carlton Best, 2018). Furthermore, the understanding of “evolutionary need for cults” means that cults provide their members with a false sense of comfort. Cults are established in a way to completely isolate their

members from the society, but their members are still provided with all the resources they need for survival. For example, in a cult named “Heaven’s Gate” their members were isolated from the rest of the society, and were living together in a big and comfortable mansion(Mantro, 2022). Moreover, many other cults use a technique where their members live together in a big house, which creates a false sense of comfort and a bond between the members. Cult members feel belonged, they see that they are not alone and other members have also gone through traumas and they are all here to understand their purpose and find answers to their questions (Carlton Best, 2018). In addition, the isolation that is created by cults results in their members to be isolated from their problems which creates a thought that cults help their members to escape from problems around them, and that it is better to stay in cult, because it provides with comfort, community, purpose and helps to “escape from the problems” (Carlton Best, 2018). One of the reasons why cults are so powerful is because they provide basic human needs and a false sense of comfort, but how is unquestioning obedience and loyalty of the cult members to cult leaders can be explained? An experiment in 1960 by Stanley Milgram brought out the result. This result showed that when the experimenter told the most ordinary people to apply electric shocks on innocent strangers, two third of the people completely obeyed the examiner and were ready to do it. This experiment was called “Obedience”(Stein, 2016). This experiment provides a deeper insight into the human mind, allowing us to understand that the majority of people tend to unquestionably listen and obey to a more dominant person. Similarly, cult leaders and the dominion that they have created around their figures, cult leaders establish a “comfort” environment, where they provide their members with basic human needs and promise to give purpose and sense of belonging, along with “giving answers” to questions that concern cult members. Social Psychology study, done by Alexandra Stein results in the claim which suggests that these; “[...] scholars understood the power of extreme social influence to corral and corrupt even the most ordinary of individuals. Totalism works because ordinary people – at least those without prior knowledge of the controlling methods of totalism – are subject to the coercive manipulations that leaders employ. If the situation is strong and isolating enough, without any clear escape route, then the average person can cave into the traumatizing pressures of brainwashing” (Stein, 2016). Cult leaders know how to manipulate others very subtly. Their manipulations are aimed at gaining complete control over the cult members. For example, their tactics are so subtle that one of the methods used by cult leaders; “involves someone sitting in a chair surrounded by other members, at which time they are required to admit their recent failures, base thoughts, shortcomings, etc” (Online Psychology Degree Guide, n.d.). Concluding all the above, the dynamic of cults “[...] can be particularly appealing to individuals who have

experienced trauma or insecurity in their personal relationships, as the cult leader provides a sense of safety and protection. Freud's theory of the unconscious can also help to explain the manipulation and brainwashing techniques used by cult leaders. By tapping into the unconscious desires and motivations of their followers, leaders are able to manipulate and control them, often to their own benefit. This can result in a distorted sense of reality and a heightened sense of devotion to the cult and its leader. Additionally, the idea of transference can also be applied to cults. Transference refers to the unconscious redirection of emotions, desires, and beliefs from one person to another. In the context of cults, transference often occurs between the cult leader and the followers, leading to a strong emotional bond between the two parties. This bond can be further reinforced by shared rituals, beliefs, and experiences” (cultdatabase, n.d.).

Similar pattern appears to exist between the people who join cults; this pattern suggests that individuals join cults because of a variety of vulnerabilities. These people seem to look for comfort and community, they are also driven by a desire to find clear answers to the questions about the world around them. A study on cults explains that people who join cults are driven by seeking comfort, they look for something that can provide solutions for their anxieties (Shane, 2022). To add on, these people are trying to understand their individual purpose and belonging. Therefore, this becomes a reason why many people around the world intensively join cults. Therefore, cult members are convinced about their special mission and are superior among the non-cult members, cults fulfill the need of individual purpose and belonging (Shane, 2022). In addition, Steven Hassan suggests; “No one joins a cult voluntarily; they are recruited into it. There is lack of informed consent. Everyone has vulnerabilities. Possible situational vulnerabilities include illness, the death of a loved one, breakup of an important relationship, loss of a job, or moving to another city, state or country. Individual vulnerabilities may include high hypnotizability, strong ability for concentration and vivid imagination, learning disorders, or autism spectrum disorders” (Hassan, 2021). Individuals who have joined cults are typically the ones that have gone through traumas and are following their desire to find a community where they can feel love and belonging. Referring to the ability of cult leaders to gain full control over their members and the reasons behind why people join cults, it is important to identify how the practices established by cult leaders affect the mind and behavior of cult members. The mind controlling tactics used by cult leaders, allow them to erase boundaries between reality and cult life. Therefore, cults affect mind and behavior by pursuing a false sense of comfort which results in cult members to have complete obedience to their leaders. Lennon writes; “Promoting an “us” against “them” mentality in this way means that should cult members

disagree with any of the actions or mantras of their group, they are unlikely to voice them for fear of alienation. Over time, suppressing these emotions leads to the stubborn irrationality [...]” (Lennon, 2019). Moreover, cult members must completely obey their leaders. Cult members are discouraged from criticizing or questioning their leaders or else they are going to get punished. In addition, cult leaders tend to “prevent both vertical and horizontal integration from happening”(Lennon, 2019). This causes negative emotions to stay inside cult members' minds, which results in trauma. Therefore, cults tend to cause their members to become mentally incapacitated; “[...] their members in this way allows a strict following mentality to flourish as suppressing emotional processing and critical thinking not only keeps them vulnerable, but also unquestioning of their leader” (Lennon, 2019). As a result, individuals join cults due to different vulnerabilities, these people often seek for comfort, where they can have a community and feel belonged and fulfill their desire of finding the answers to their questions. From all the above, cults result in harmful effects on the brain of the members, which is caused due to practices that distort critical thinking and inhibit emotions, which allows cult leaders to gain a full control over their members. (Lennon, 2019).

To understand the mindset of cult members and leaders, professionals most often identify the triggers that created internal conflict, thereby forcing them to create or join cults. In addition, additional professionals also rely on internal needs and impulses that drive cult leaders to establish cults. According to Sigmund Freud; “[...] human behavior is driven by unconscious desires and motivations. He believed that individuals are driven by instinctual forces, including the sexual and aggressive impulses, and that these impulses are often in conflict with the constraints of society. In cults, this conflict can be magnified as individuals surrender their individual identity and autonomy to the group. Cults often attract individuals who are searching for meaning and purpose in their lives. Freud referred to this as the "narcissistic wound," or the feeling of emptiness and lack of fulfillment that many individuals experience. [...] Freud also noted the power dynamics present in human relationships, including the role of authority figures and the urge to submit to their will. In cults, the leader or leaders often assume a god-like or messianic role, exerting complete control over the lives of their followers” (cultdatabase, n.d.). Most often, cult leaders are considered to be the real evil, they are non-sensual monsters who injure their plots. While this is partly true, cult leaders are also broken and repressed people. Therefore, cult leaders are also victims of not being accepted by society, feelings of loneliness, and looking for a community that can provide them with “love”. For example, Marshall Applewhite, a founder of a cult named “Heaven’s Gate” (Mantro, 2022). Marshall was married with two children, he taught at the University of St. Marshall lived in the family of an ordinary life, until one day, that

changed everything. It turned out that Marshall had a romance with a student, because of which Marshall's wife divorced him with a scandal, moving, she forbade Marshall to communicate with their children. Marshall also lost his job and everyone turned away from him, he was left alone, having low self-respect and hope for the best.

Without the proper treatment that Marshall needed, his condition worsened, and he soon began to "see" the alien intelligence that prompted him to create the cult "Heaven's gate" (Mantro, 2022). People who have escaped or been rescued from cults tend to suffer from different disorders, which are results of trauma caused by negative emotions experienced and identity disturbance. For example, cult abuse; "can result in significant psychological harm, including anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and suicidal thoughts"(No Fear Counselling, n.d.). Cult leaders also need treatment, often they themselves become victims of various traumas and upheavals. Therefore, the resulting traumas caused by internal conflict and cults needed to be treated, these traumas cannot be triggered harder, and the received post cult effects will only further worsen the mental health of cult leaders and people who came out of cults. There are different examples of therapies for people who have come out from the cults, for example:

- **Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT)** is an evidence-based approach to treatment that focuses on how people's thoughts, emotions, and beliefs influence their behavior and how they perceive themselves (Insight Psychological, n.d.).
- **Mindfulness Therapy** is an approach to treatment that focuses on how people's thoughts, emotions, and beliefs influence their behavior and how they perceive themselves, others, and the world. The ability to be in the moment, to acknowledge and regulate your emotions helps you to break free from negative thought patterns (Insight Psychological, n.d.).
- **Dialectical Behaviour Therapy (DBT)** is a treatment method that is similar to cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) but emphasizes building skills to manage stress, mental health issues, and the psycho-social aspects of relationship building (Insight Psychological, n.d.).
- **Emotionally Focused Therapy** is based on observations and experience. It looks at emotions and emotional intelligence, which helps support stronger and more secure relationships by helping better understand how our actions impact others, and how our emotions drive our interaction (Insight Psychological, n.d.).
- **Family Systems Therapy** looks at the family as one emotional unit. This therapeutic approach looks at the relationships within the family and the structure as a whole (Insight Psychological, n.d.).
- **Grief Work Therapy** refers to the methods used in counseling that help people to grieve loss and understand their emotions associated with the loss in a healthy way with the ultimate goal of moving forward (Insight Psychological, n.d.).

Finally, exploration of cults through psychological approaches has let to understand

That cult attracts numbers of individuals who seek to find comfort and belonging. Human drive to join cults is a result of vulnerabilities and traumas experienced, cult leaders provide their members with false sense of comfort and promise to provide with purpose and community. The resulting psychological effects are negative emotions being stuck resulting in trauma, difficulty of critical thinking, identity disturbance and more. Both cult members and

leaders need to be treated. The resulting traumas caused by internal conflict and cults needed to be treated, these traumas cannot be triggered harder, and the received post cult effects will only further worsen the mental health of cult leaders and people who came out of cults.

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